

Electronic Pharmacies and Consumer Protection: National and International Legal Aspects

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Abstract: The article examines the topical issue of consumer protection of pharmaceutical services, in particular, in the context of e-pharmacies, which has become particularly important in the context of rapid development of electronic (digital) commerce. The purpose of the study is to analyse the main challenges and threats faced by consumers when purchasing pharmaceutical products online, and to identify ways to improve protective mechanisms at the national and international levels. The methods of analysis, synthesis, comparison, modelling and abstraction were used in the study. This approach allowed the authors to identify the main legal issues related to the operation of e-pharmacies and to describe the existing international legal standards of consumer protection in different countries of the world. Based on the analysis of the current law enforcement practice of certain countries, it is established that users of e-pharmacies still face significant risks associated with the circulation of counterfeit or low-quality medicines, violation of personal data confidentiality and manipulative commercial practices. The authors emphasises the need for comprehensive cooperation between international organisations, states, businesses and consumers to create common safety standards and effective consumer protection in the digital environment.

Keywords: consumer protection, consumers, e-pharmacy, business entities, economic activity, international standards, service, control, healthcare, authorities.

1. Introduction

Since the first online pharmacies appeared in the late 1990s, the pharmaceutical market has undergone significant transformations. The rapid development of digital technologies, the proliferation of e-commerce, the growth of Internet access and the overall digitalisation of healthcare services have stimulated the active expansion of the e-commerce segment of the pharmaceutical market. Online pharmacies became widespread during the COVID-19 pandemic, when consumer behaviour was redefined and a new approach to purchasing medicines in the digital environment was formed. As a result, e-pharmacies have become an important part of the healthcare system in many countries.

Today, online pharmacies function as a supplement to traditional pharmacies or as fully autonomous digital platforms capable of processing orders and delivering medicines, including those based on electronic prescriptions. E-commerce features provide these market players with much wider geographical reach than classical institutions, allowing them to cover even those regions where there is no pharmacy infrastructure.

Despite the obvious advantages of e-retail of medicines, such as convenience for consumers, increased access to pharmaceutical products and time savings, this area is accompanied by a number of serious risks. These include the sale of uncertified or counterfeit medicines, lack of proper quality control, violation of consumers' rights to confidentiality and secure contractual terms, and limited legal remedies in the event of disputes. An additional complication is the lack of a unified approach to regulating the activities of Internet pharmacies and other entities providing electronic pharmaceutical services at the international level, which makes it difficult to effectively combat offences in this area. According to the International Pharmaceutical Federation [1], only 49% of countries have legislative provisions regulating this type of activity, while in many regions, in particular in Africa and Southeast Asia, there is no such regulation. Thus, in the context of the rapid development of online commerce, the issue of ensuring an appropriate level of consumer protection, in particular, guaranteeing their right to purchase safe, effective and legalised medicines via the Internet, is of particular importance.

A review of the current scientific literature shows that despite the growing interest in e-pharmacies, most publications focus on specific aspects of this topic. In particular, researchers examine the digital transformation of pharmaceutical services [2], study the behavioural factors that influence consumer choice [3], analyse the criteria for service quality [4], assess the risks associated with the manufacture and sale of low-quality or dangerous medicines [5], and draw attention to legislative gaps in this area [6; 7]. At the same time, some scientific works are devoted to the protection of patients' rights in the provision of pharmaceutical services, in particular, determining the subject composition of these legal relations, clarifying the specifics of their provision, identifying types of violations of patients' rights and mechanisms for their legal protection [8; 9; 10]. However, there is still a lack of research that systematically considers consumer protection in the context of e-pharmacies. A comparative analysis of national legal systems and international standards, as well as the problems of their harmonisation, is particularly relevant. This is confirmed by a study by Bessell et al. [11], which analysed the effectiveness of online pharmacies and the specifics of control over websites selling medicines at the national and transnational levels. The researchers came to the right conclusion that providing consumers with an adequate level of safety and quality of electronic pharmaceutical services is a serious challenge for states.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to analyse the problem of consumer protection in e-pharmacies through the prism of national and international legal regulation, and to formulate proposals for improving the relevant protection mechanisms. The hypothesis of the study is that legal fragmentation, imperfect regulatory instruments and insufficient supervision in the field of electronic pharmaceutical commerce pose significant risks to consumers. The main conclusion is that only the interaction of international organisations, government institutions, business and consumers themselves can ensure an effective and safe model of e-pharmacy in the global environment.

2. Materials and Methods

The study applies an interdisciplinary approach to the analysis of legal protection of consumer rights in the field of electronic retail trade in medicines. The study is based on a thorough examination of legal frameworks, including national legislation, international legal instruments, and soft law documents issued by organisations such as the United Nations, World Health Organisation, OECD, and UNCTAD. In addition, information from official analytical reports, law enforcement practice, and academic literature in the field of medical, pharmaceutical, and information law, electronic (digital) commerce, and consumer protection was used.

To achieve these goals, a combination of general scientific and specialised legal methods was used. The method of logical and structural analysis helped to systematise the sources and identify the key issues of legal regulation of electronic pharmacy trade. The comparative legal method allowed to study different models of legal support for consumers in different countries and identify best practices and shortcomings of certain regulatory approaches.

The generalisation method helped to formulate recommendations for improving the regulatory environment. The modelling method was used to create the author's proposals for harmonising national legislation with international standards. The methods of abstraction and legal forecasting were used to formulate theoretical conclusions, in particular, to assess the prospects for the evolution of the legal regime for electronic commerce in medicines in the context of digitalisation.

In addition, elements of content analysis were used to analyse the effectiveness of the current regulation, covering both the legislative framework and academic sources. The approach based on the interaction of legal doctrine and law enforcement practice helped to ensure an understanding of the issues and form a comprehensive view of the research object.

The proposed methodology made it possible to cover the legal, organisational, socio-economic aspects of the functioning of electronic pharmacies, which became the basis for formulating conclusions and proposals for improving legal regulation in this area.

3. Results and Discussion

A. Modern challenges for e-pharmacy consumers in the e-commerce era

The development of digital technologies is significantly transforming the usual patterns of consumer behaviour, stimulating the active expansion of e-commerce. Thanks to the emergence of mobile devices with Internet access, consumers have gained unimpeded access to digital markets, including online pharmacies, which are rapidly integrating into global economic processes. In the digital era, consumers are not only key elements of market systems and mechanisms [12], but also have a significant impact on macroeconomic indicators: according to

the OECD, the share of consumer spending in GDP in member countries reaches 60%, and the volume of daily transactions is estimated at hundreds of billions of dollars [13].

E-pharmacies have become a convenient alternative to traditional points of sale of medicines. The main advantages of this format include the ability to check the availability of medicines without visiting several pharmacies, which is especially important when searching for medicines for rare diseases; accessibility for residents of remote areas and people with disabilities; saving time and resources; a wide range of products, including related products; and the provision of additional services, such as remote consultations with a pharmacist, information on drug interactions, availability of analogues and price comparisons [6]. In addition, users can compare offers, read reviews from other customers and make informed decisions.

Despite the obvious advantages, the dynamic development of e-pharmacy is accompanied by a number of challenges, including violations of fundamental consumer rights. This situation creates an urgent need for proper legal regulation and effective protection of consumers' interests in the digital space. The issue of consumer rights protection in the field of online trade in medicines has gained a significant international response. In particular, the UN General Assembly Resolution 70/186 [14] calls on Member States to develop effective policies in this area that ensure a level of security not lower than in traditional trade. The document outlines a number of key principles: access to essential goods, protection of vulnerable groups, product safety, consumer awareness, price transparency, access to justice and redress mechanisms, etc.

The OECD in its recommendations [14] for business also emphasises the need to introduce standards of transparency, honesty in advertising, provision of complete information about goods, payment security, dispute resolution and personal data protection.

At the same time, there is an uneven development of e-commerce legislation globally in terms of consumer protection. According to UBCTAD [15], only 115 out of 142 countries that provided data have a regulatory framework governing e-commerce. In Europe, the number of such countries is 78%, in Africa - 52%, and in the Americas - 71%. Legislation recognising the legal equivalence of paper and electronic forms of transactions has been adopted in 158 countries (81%), mostly in developing economies. The most developed regulatory framework exists in European countries, while African countries demonstrate a much lower level of legal support in this area.

This unevenness is explained by a number of factors, including economic instability, limited digital infrastructure, lack of professional staff, and low levels of digital literacy. As a result, in some countries or regions, electronic commerce in medicines is carried out without adequate protection of the rights and interests of consumers. This state of affairs necessitates the unification of international approaches and the introduction of effective legal protection tools in the field of e-pharmacies.

B. Consumer protection in the field of electronic commerce of medicinal products

The legal regulation of e-commerce, including the activities of online pharmacies, covers most aspects of the interaction between the consumer and the seller. Conventionally, this protection can be divided into three key stages: before the purchase (provision of reliable information, content requirements, avoidance of unfair practices), during the purchase (protection of rights in contracts, secure payment instruments, confidentiality of personal data), and after the purchase (reimbursement, complaints, dispute resolution in a cross-border context) [16].

At the initial stage of making an online order, the consumer has the right to receive complete, reliable and accessible information necessary to make an informed decision on the purchase of medicines. This applies, in particular, to the seller's identification data (company name, legal address, contact details, link to the official website), return policy, information about logistics operators and delivery terms. Providing such information is a key factor in building trust in an electronic pharmacy service.

At the stage of purchase, the consumer must be protected from unfair contractual terms, fraudulent payment schemes, and the leakage of confidential information. In the context of e-commerce, the security of financial transactions becomes particularly important, since users provide personal data, including name, address, and payment information, which may be vulnerable to abuse. Criminals can use such data for illicit enrichment, theft, and fraud. The main cyber risks include unauthorized access, virus attacks, data interception, etc. In this regard, there is a need to introduce transparent procedures for processing personal data, use reliable information protection tools, and obtain clear and informed consent from the user to process his data.

At the post-purchase stage, the consumer should be able to exercise their right to a refund if the pharmaceutical product is not delivered or is delivered in an unsatisfactory condition. In addition, the buyer must be provided with the right to replace the product if it does not meet the characteristics of the order. At the same time, at this stage, there are often difficulties in interacting with online pharmacies, which complicates the exercise of consumer rights. Thus, at this stage, state regulation should provide consumers with a certain period of time to think and make a final decision when purchasing medicines online, as well as mitigate their obligations in certain cases.

Since medicines, like any other pharmaceutical product, directly affect the patient's health, it is extremely important to ensure compliance with the established quality standards, shelf life, storage and transportation conditions. Delivery is an integral part of online pharmaceutical sales, so it must be accompanied by measures to control temperature, protect against moisture, light and other external factors. Timely receipt of the drug, especially in case of emergency, is critical to preserve its therapeutic properties and treatment effectiveness.

When purchasing medicines through online pharmacies, consumers may face a number of threats related to the possible receipt of counterfeit, unregistered, invalid or expired medicines. Such medicines may contain insufficient or excessive amounts of the active ingredient, be contaminated with foreign impurities, or not contain the pharmacologically active ingredient at all. This can result not only in ineffective treatment or adverse effects, but also in serious threats to patients' lives [17; 18].

The study by Watkins et al. analysed the qualitative composition of three medicines - Piomore, Tamodex and Buprotic SR - ordered from a dubious online resource. The results showed that one of the samples did not contain the declared active ingredient, and the other did not meet the quality standards set by the FDA for generic drugs [19].

Thus, in order for a medicinal product to provide the expected therapeutic effect, it must meet high technological standards, be manufactured in a certified facility and undergo a proper quality control procedure. Only under these conditions can we guarantee a stable, effective and safe treatment result. Only high-quality pharmaceuticals, which are an integral part of an efficiently functioning healthcare system, can provide such results.

Pharmaceuticals are manufactured in both developed and developing countries. However, there is a significant difference between them in terms of regulatory control. Most economically developed countries have developed legal mechanisms and institutional systems in place to ensure

compliance with quality, efficacy and safety standards for medicines, although the specific procedures may differ. In contrast, in many developing countries, the pharmaceutical market often operates without proper regulation, resulting in serious gaps in quality control, lack of resources, training and unified standards [20].

The World Health Organisation estimates that approximately one in ten medicines sold in low- and middle-income countries is counterfeit or substandard. Due to the distribution of such products, states suffer economic losses of more than USD 30 billion annually [17]. In turn, the global market for counterfeit medicines is estimated to be worth about \$200 billion a year, with a growth rate of 20% annually, which is almost twice as high as the growth rate of the legal pharmaceutical market [21].

In response to the proliferation of counterfeit medicines, countries such as the United States of America, the European Union, the United Kingdom, Canada and Australia have taken a number of regulatory measures to strengthen control over the activities of legal online pharmacies. The main measures include certification and accreditation systems, the introduction of official logos for accredited online pharmacies, and requirements to disclose key identification information about the pharmacy: registration number, owner, head pharmacist, address, telephone number and email.

A good example of such initiatives is the introduction of a special top-level domain ‘.pharmacy’ in the United States in 2014. This system aims to provide consumers with a tool to recognise reliable and licensed online pharmacy platforms. The procedure for obtaining this domain involves several stages: applying to the National Association of Boards of Pharmacy (NABP) with an application, passing a check for compliance with the criteria and standards, including analysis of the provided documentation and website, and registering a domain name through an authorised provider - EnCirca - using a secure electronic token [22].

In addition, some countries have official state registers of online pharmacies that allow consumers to check the legitimacy and licensing status of the relevant online resource [23].

Within the European Union, Directive 2011/62/EU was adopted, according to which the European Commission approved Regulation No. 699/2014 [24], which establishes visual and identifying elements of a single logo for officially registered e-pharmacies. According to the Regulation, starting from 1 July 2015, all online pharmacies authorised to operate in the EU, as well as in Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein, are required to display the unified European logo on their websites. In addition, they must be registered in the relevant national register of the Member State where the pharmacy is located.

Each online pharmacy is obliged to place on its website a hyperlink to the relevant entry in the national register confirming its authority to sell medicinal products remotely in accordance with the law. The website of the Member State's supervisory authority must be integrated with the website of the European Medicines Agency (EMA), which contains a consolidated database of all authorised e-pharmacies that are entitled to operate within the EU. The presence of an online pharmacy in the official register not only confirms its legality, but also serves as a tool to increase consumer confidence and reduce the risk of purchasing low-quality or counterfeit medicines [24].

Despite the existence of formal mechanisms for identifying e-pharmacies, the problem of identifying illegal web resources remains relevant. Illegal pharmaceutical platforms continue to operate actively and, using search engine optimisation techniques, disguise themselves as legitimate resources. The study conducted by Fittler and his colleagues analysed the activities of 136 online pharmacies over a period of four years. The researchers found significant discrepancies

between the declared domain location and the actual physical location of servers by IP address. Therefore, they concluded that most of these platforms operated outside the legal framework, disregarded ethical standards of pharmaceutical activities, and therefore posed a potential threat to patients [25].

Fraudulent online pharmacies are actively using aggressive digital marketing tools, including manipulative advertising, unfair search engine optimisation and fake rankings to improve their visibility online, making it much more difficult for the average consumer to recognise illegal resources [26].

In addition, many illegal online pharmacies deliberately create a visual imitation of officially registered and licensed institutions. Such resources may deliberately display attributes that purport to indicate their origin from countries with high standards of quality control and safety of pharmaceutical products. However, in practice, the medicines sold by these platforms are often manufactured without proper compliance with manufacturing standards, which casts doubt on their efficacy and safety. As a result, such drugs may be of poor quality, expired, counterfeit, and therefore dangerous to the health of the consumer.

In addition to threats related to product quality, both legal and illegal online pharmacies actively exploit the vulnerability of certain categories of consumers. These include demographic, psychosocial, individual, systemic and situational factors that affect the consumer's ability to make informed decisions [27]. For example, user reviews on e-pharmacy websites can be seen as a tool to ensure transparency. At the same time, there is a risk of manipulation: unscrupulous sellers often post fake reviews to artificially increase their own reputation or discredit competitors.

Another problem is the aggressive marketing campaigns implemented by online pharmacies to encourage self-diagnosis. Such strategies encourage consumers to choose medicines without proper medical advice, which increases the risk of taking inadequate medicines. In some cases, pharmaceutical products are offered without a prescription, even if a doctor's prescription is required. This practice not only poses a potential health risk to patients, but also undermines trust in the healthcare system by reducing the treatment process to a mere consumer act.

In a number of countries, the sale of prescription medicines through e-pharmacies is prohibited or strictly regulated by law. The sale of such medicines without a valid doctor's prescription is considered a violation of the law. However, despite the existing legal restrictions, many online pharmacies operate without a licence and do not comply with the established regulatory requirements for the circulation of medicines. Often, such resources sell medicines that require a prescription without providing medical documents or consulting a specialist. In addition, the products on offer often include uncertified drugs of unknown origin, with improper dosage of active ingredients or dangerous impurities, which endangers the health of consumers.

According to a study conducted in a number of European countries, including Denmark, Germany, the United Kingdom, Spain and Sweden, cases of purchasing prescription drugs online without a prescription were recorded. In particular, 4.1 % of respondents reported purchasing opioid drugs, 7.6 % - stimulants, and 2.7 % - sedatives [28].

In a study by Fittler and colleagues that analysed 136 e-pharmacy websites, it was found that the vast majority (88.2%) offered the sale of prescription drugs. However, only 6.6 per cent of these sites required a prescription, while 38.2 per cent did not ask for any medical information from customers. At the same time, websites operating in the OTC format demonstrated stable activity and growth [25].

A study conducted by Monteith and Glenn found that people who try to purchase psychotropic drugs online often become customers of dubious pharmacy platforms. Such online resources, as a rule, do not require a prescription and use unreliable documents to confirm their accreditation [29].

At the same time, even the purchase of medicines through online pharmacies that appear to be officially registered does not always provide consumers with protection against counterfeit products. For example, in the UK, there have been cases where counterfeit medicines sold through online platforms and properly packaged have been found in offline pharmacies and sometimes in medical institutions [30].

Although national laws, policies and practical mechanisms of individual countries can partially deter fraud, manipulation and unfair commercial behaviour in the online trade in medicines, ensuring effective control at the international level remains a serious challenge. Since the jurisdiction of each state extends exclusively to its territory, countries are not able to independently establish legal requirements for the activities of foreign online pharmacies that sell medicines on their market. As a result, there is a situation of regulatory ambiguity and conflicts between national approaches to regulation, which makes it difficult to combat cross-border violations in the field of electronic pharmaceutical trade.

Differences in the procedures for licensing, circulation and quality control of medicines in different countries further complicate the work of international and national law enforcement agencies. This situation often leads to interstate legal conflicts, as national regulators have virtually no authority to act outside their own territory [31]. Therefore, ensuring consumer safety and quality assurance of medicines in e-commerce outside the jurisdiction of a single state is a complex task that requires international coordination.

Many Internet resources that function as online pharmacies have a complex digital architecture that includes numerous duplicate pages (mirrors) and redirects to other websites. This complex structure significantly complicates the process of identification and oversight by regulators and researchers, which creates additional challenges for ensuring the legality and transparency of such platforms.

One of the main problems in the field of consumer protection of electronic pharmaceutical services both at the national and international levels remains the lack of proper legal regulation and constant monitoring of e-pharmacies. This problem makes it impossible to properly guarantee the quality, legality and safety of medicines sold online, as well as to verify the legality of the activities of the relevant business entities.

Effective consumer protection of consumer rights in the context of the digitalisation of the pharmaceutical sector requires coordinated interaction between national authorities, international organisations and business representatives. International institutions play an important role in this process, developing unified approaches, standards and recommendations aimed at ensuring the transparency and safety of online pharmacies. The task of governments is to adapt these international norms and standards to domestic legislation, develop an effective national regulatory framework and create effective mechanisms to monitor compliance.

At the same time, business representatives, especially pharmaceutical companies, are obliged to comply with the established norms and implement corporate responsibility practices. Blockchain technology is one of the most promising tools that is seen as an effective means of combating the falsification of medicines. This technology is seen as a potentially transformative

framework capable of modernising pharmaceutical supply chains, making them more reliable, transparent, controlled and counterfeit-proof [33].

The use of blockchain solutions ensures the availability of verified digital records for each transaction, which allows for accurate tracking of the movement of medicines in the supply chain [34]. One example of the implementation of such technology is the MediLedger project, launched in 2017 by Pfizer and Genentech. Its goal is to create a secure blockchain network for the exchange of information between supply chain participants, which allows for the traceability of pharmaceutical products and the detection of counterfeit drugs [35].

In addition, a number of independent organisations operate in the pharmaceutical market to verify the reliability of online resources specialising in the sale of medicines. This includes the LegitScript platform, which monitors the activities of online pharmacies, focusing on compliance with regulatory requirements, transparency of operations and consumer rights [36].

Just as leading consumer protection organisations such as the Bureau Européen des Unions de Consommateurs (BEUC, Belgium), Consumers Japan, Consumers New Zealand, CUTS International (Geneva office), Organización de Consumidores y Usuarios de Chile (ODECU), and the International Chamber of Commerce of Chile (ICC, Geneva office) together with representatives of the private sector and the World Trade Organisation (WTO), have joined forces to overcome challenges in the field of consumer protection in e-commerce [37], and similar joint initiatives should be introduced by key players in the global pharmaceutical market. Such cross-sectoral cooperation will not only contribute to more effective consumer protection, but will also meet the strategic interests of the pharmaceutical industry.

The joint activities of regulators, civil society and the business community can form the basis for the development of unified international standards for the operation of e-pharmacies. Such standards could potentially form the basis of a global regulatory system for online pharmacy sales. This, in turn, will create the conditions for effective counteraction to the falsification of pharmaceutical products, elimination of unfair competition and improvement of the quality of service, which will have a positive impact on both the rights and safety of consumers and the stability of the pharmaceutical market as a whole.

In this context, special attention should be paid to raising consumer awareness. Having basic knowledge of how to identify a legitimate and compliant e-pharmacy can reduce the risk of purchasing counterfeit or uncertified medicines that may pose a threat to life and health. An example of a successful awareness-raising initiative is the FDA's BeSafeRx: Your Source for Online Pharmacy Information campaign, which aims to raise awareness among the public and healthcare professionals about the dangers associated with purchasing medicines online. As part of this campaign, consumers are provided with practical advice on how to safely choose an e-pharmacy and make online orders [38].

Consumer awareness plays an important role in making the right decisions about the choice of medicines and their safe use. When consumers have access to complete and accurate information about the composition, dosage, side effects and contraindications of pharmaceutical products, they are able to make informed decisions. This reduces the likelihood of self-treatment errors, increases the effectiveness of therapy, and helps build trust in e-pharmacies as a safe and convenient source of medical products.

4. Conclusions

The active development of e-commerce in medicines, in particular the development of online pharmacies, is accompanied by new challenges in the area of consumer protection. In the digital environment, there is a growing need to create an effective legal mechanism capable of ensuring proper consumer protection at both national and transnational levels..

The most pressing challenges that need to be addressed include: insufficient access to complete and accurate information about medicines, their manufacturers and distributors; unethical marketing practices; imposition of unfavourable terms on consumers when entering into contracts; risks associated with breaches of personal data confidentiality; and unreliable security systems for online payments. An additional threat is posed by difficulties related to pre-trial dispute resolution mechanisms, compensation for damages, and delivery of goods of proper quality. Particular attention should be paid to ensuring the proper quality of the medicinal products themselves, including compliance with standards for physical and chemical properties, certification, transportation and storage of products sold in electronic format.

Given these challenges, it can be concluded that consumers who purchase medicines from e-pharmacies are currently not sufficiently protected. In this regard, it is important to coordinate efforts between international and national institutions, as well as to establish cooperation between consumers and businesses.

International organisations have the potential to play a leading role in developing unified standards and recommendations aimed at increasing the transparency, security and legitimacy of e-pharmacies. National authorities, in turn, should adapt these standards to domestic legislation, ensure proper oversight and create effective enforcement mechanisms.

The pharmaceutical business is responsible for complying with the established standards, implementing ethical and responsible practices and creating a safe environment for consumers. At the same time, consumer awareness plays a key role in ensuring their rights: awareness of the risks, channels for checking the legitimacy of e-pharmacies and rules for safe online ordering of medicines is an important prerequisite for secure and effective access to medicines in the digital age.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interests. All authors read and approved final version of the paper.

Authors Contribution

All authors contributed equally in this paper.

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